

Polifonia: a digital harmoniser for musical heritage knowledge, H2020

D7.5 DMP webinar on long term preservation

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Project information

Project Start Date: 1st of January 2021

Project Duration: 40 months

Project website: <http://www.polifonia-project.eu>

Project contacts

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POLIFONIA consortium

No.	Short name	Institution name	Country
1	UNIBO	ALMA MATER STUDIORUM - UNIVERSITÀ DI BOLOGNA	Italy
2	OU	THE OPEN UNIVERSITY	United Kingdom
3	KCL	KING'S COLLEGE LONDON	United Kingdom
4	NUI GALWAY	NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND GALWAY	Ireland
5	MiC	MINISTERO DELLA CULTURA	Italy
6	CNRS	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	France
	SORBONNE	SORBONNE UNIVERSITE (LinkedTP)	France
7	CNAM	CONSERVATOIRE NATIONAL DES ARTS ET METIERS	France
8	NISV	STICHTING NEDERLANDS INSTITUUT VOORBEELD EN GELUID	Netherlands

9	KNAW	KONINKLIJKE NEDERLANDSE AKADEMIE VAN WETENSCHAPPEN	Netherlands
10	DP	DIGITAL PATHS SRL	Italy

Project Summary

European musical heritage is a dynamic historical flow of experiences, leaving heterogeneous traces that are difficult to capture, connect, access, interpret, and valorise. Computing technologies have the potential to shed a light on this wealth of resources by extracting, materialising and linking new knowledge from heterogeneous sources, hence revealing facts and experiences from hidden voices of the past. Polifonia makes this happen by building novel ways of inspecting, representing, and interacting with digital content. Memory institutions, scholars, and citizens will be able to navigate, explore, and discover multiple perspectives and stories about European Musical Heritage.

Polifonia focuses on European Musical Heritage, intended as musical contents and artefacts - or music objects - (tunes, scores, melodies, notations, etc.) along with relevant knowledge about them such as: their links to tangible objects (theatres, conservatoires, churches, etc.), their cultural and historical contexts, opinions and stories told by people having diverse social and artistic roles (scholars, writers, students, intellectuals, musicians, politicians, journalists, etc), and facts expressed in different styles and disciplines (memoire, reportage, news, biographies, reviews), different languages (English, Italian, French, Spanish, and German), and across centuries.

The overall goal of the project is to realise an ecosystem of computational methods and tools supporting discovery, extraction, encoding, interlinking, classification, exploration of, and access to, musical heritage knowledge on the Web. An equally important objective is to demonstrate that these tools improve the state of the art of Social Science and Humanities (SSH) methodologies. Hence their development is guided by, and continuously intertwined with, experiments and validations performed in real-world settings, identified by musical heritage stakeholders (both belonging to the Consortium and external supporters) such as cultural institutes and collection owners, historians of music, anthropologists and ethnomusicologists, linguists, etc.

Executive summary

Towards the end of the project, Polifonia planned to hold a webinar which original title was 'D7.5 DMP webinar on long term preservation'.

During the last consortium meeting in Bologna October 2023, we extensively discussed how to foster the impact of the project in academia and beyond. How to make the output of Polifonia sustainable after the lifetime of the project is one important aspect. But fostering re-usability does not end by long-term preservation of certain assets (such as data and tools). In this webinar, we also discuss how we ensure that more fluid assets such as interfaces, but also experiences in setting up and executing workflows via those interfaces, become reproducible and reuseable.

This webinar presents the specific Data Management Strategy (set up as management of research components of the type Data, Tools and Reports) Polifonia has developed. We present the project briefly and detail the Polifonia Research Ecosystem as our DMP strategy. We also summarise how the Ecosystem approach is related to usual DMP practices.

In the last one-third of the webinar, we ask a round of experts to

- give feedback to the presentations
- share their own experiences with making project output sustainable by fostering reusability
- share ideas with us how to improve our impact strategy in Polifonia

This report contains the programme and closes with a short summary of the discussion and action points. All presentations are added as annexes.

Document History

Version	Release date	Summary of changes	Author(s) -Institution
V0.1	24/01/2024	First draft released	KNAW
V0.2	28/01/2024	Comments from panelists and chair included	KNAW, OU, NISV
V0.9	29/01/2024	Version submitted to the coordinator	KNAW
V1.0	dd/mm/yyyy	Final version submitted to REA	UNIBO

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Polifonia Research Ecosystem – Impact of a project: A webinar on Data re-use and workflows (Programme)

January 19, 2024: 13.00-14.30 Amsterdam time

Polifonia Research Ecosystem – Impact of a project A webinar on Data re-use and workflows

Motivation

Towards the end of the project, Polifonia planned to hold a webinar which original title was ‘D7.5 DMP webinar on long term preservation’. During the last consortium meeting in Bologna October 2023, we extensively discussed how to foster the impact of the project in academia and beyond. How to make the output of Polifonia sustainable after the lifetime of the project is one important aspect. But fostering re-usability does not end by long-term preservation of certain assets (such as data and tools). In this webinar we will also discuss how we ensure that more fluid assets such as interfaces, but also experiences in setting up and executing workflows via those interfaces, become reproducible and reuseable.

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- give feedback to the presentations
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- share ideas with us how to improve our impact strategy in Polifonia

Schedule

13.00-13.15 Introduction into the project and thoughts on (long-term) impact of the Polifonia project (Peter van Kranenburg)

13.15-13.45 The Research Ecosystem approach of the Polifonia project (Enrico Daga)

13.45-14.00 The dynamic nature of Data Management in a research project (Andrea Scharnhorst)

14.00-14.30 Panel round with experts from other projects and ERIC’s (lead by Elena Giglia, Head of the Open Access Office at the University of Turin and Polifonia Advisory Board member)

Panel members:

Dr. Femmy Admiraal - Senior data management expert at Leiden University Libraries

Dr. Suzanne Dumochel - Head of International Cooperation, CNRS (Directorate of Open Research Data)

Barbara Magagna – coauthor of the FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP) Ontology, and member of the EOSC Task Force Semantic Interoperability (confirmed)

Conclusions

The webinar was advertised on various channels: Polifonia internal and Stakeholder Network mailing list, Polifonia website, Twitter, LinkedIN; but also, on the CLARIAH.nl (a Dutch infrastructure project), and the DARIAH ERIC channels. It was further announced at the FAIRImpact¹, MuseIT² and the EuropeanaTech³ mailing lists. The webinar was attended by 44 participants. The majority of the audience were researchers active in Polifonia (about 30%), or from came from institutions being part of the Polifonia consortium (40%), and 30% were researchers from other projects.

In the (panel) discussion, it was emphasized that Polifonia has taken an interesting innovative approach to Data Management concerning two different aspects:

- (1) Polifonia introduced a philosophy of science perspective to Data Management – reflecting about the why and how of Data Management. This helps to better understand some of the recurring frictions when it comes to the execution of Research Data Management in interdisciplinary projects. But, it also puts Data Management in a wider context of knowledge management in complex collaborative settings. One could call this ‘Data in Context’. Being aware of this wider context can help to improve the quality of Data management planning and execution.
- (2) Polifonia used its own methodological approaches (semantic web technologies, machine readable and open linked data) to create a machine-executable Data Management (Plan). Following what has been expressed under point 1 (namely to document “Data in Context”), the formalization of the DMP goes beyond existing solutions to fill the usual question-based DMP templates. Polifonia connected DATA, with TOOLS, and REPORTS. These three main categories hold a variety of well defined ‘research components’, together with a clear annotation scheme for them, and a transparent archiving (and versioning) workflow. This comprehensive approach is called the *Polifonia Research Ecosystem* (see <https://polifonia-project.github.io/ecosystem/>). The Ecosystem represents a middle layer for machine-readable description of ‘research components’ residing above the more granular level of research objects (as captured e.g. by RO-CRATE⁴), and the usual higher level of executing project management such as Workpackages, tasks and their interdependencies. In essence, it translates between the more granular level and the functional higher level, by using an annotation scheme which brings information about the actual research object and its function to solve a research question in a project together. On a practical level, it also enables an overview about all

¹ FAIRImpact is one of the major EOSC infrastructure projects on FAIR recommendations. <https://fair-impact.eu>

² MuseIT being a related, newer research project, <https://www.muse-it.eu>, Multisensory, User-centred, Shared cultural Experiences through Interactive Technologies 2022 - 2025

³ [EuropeanaTech](https://europeanatech.eu) is the community of experts, developers, and researchers from the cultural heritage R&D sector within the greater Europeana Network Association.

⁴ <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/>

components (including DATA), their curation and their interdependencies; supporting the DMP documentation.

From the two main points mentioned above, a couple of actions follows:

- Publish about the approach scientifically parallel in computer science and information science venues, expose the approach to a wider scientific discourse
- Explore overlap and differences, maybe possible links to (machine actionable) approaches provided by the GO-FAIR and other similar organization, which aim to support FAIRness and Data Stewardship. For that look in particular at: FAIR Implementation Profiles: <https://fip-wizard.ds-wizard.org/> and participate in the FAIR Digital Object Forum - FAIR Implementation Profiles Practice Group
- Seek connection to ERIC's which operate in the area of research/knowledge organization and research infrastructures in the Humanities /cultural heritage domain such as DARIAH⁵ and OPERAS⁶

We take care of these actions in the future remaining deliverables and planned publications, and by participation in DARIAH.EU (via a DARIAH Working group), and the EOSC Task Force on Semantic Interoperability. We also use current participation in other projects, such as MuseIT, SPICE, FAIRImpact and others.

The (edited) video of this webinar will be published in the Polifonia YouTube channel. The report and all presentations will be made open via the Polifonia Zenodo community.

⁵ <https://www.dariah.eu>

⁶ <https://operas-eu.org>

Annexes

Introduction to the webinar

The slide features a black background with a network of blue and purple lines and circles. The Polifonia logo is in the top left. The main text is centered in white. At the bottom left, there is a small European Union flag icon followed by a disclaimer.

 Polifonia

Polifonia Research Ecosystem – Impact of a project

A webinar on Data re-use and workflows

January 19, 2024 13.00-14.30 Amsterdam time

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The communication reflects only the author's view and the Research Executive Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

**Note: this Live Meeting is being recorded.
By participating in this meeting,
you agree that your communications may be recorded.
The purpose of recording the meeting is to save and
archive this information in light of the Polifonia project.
The video will be uploaded to our YouTube channel and
distributed among those who found themselves unable to join today.**

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**Chair of the meeting
Dr. Elena Giglia, Head of the Open Access Office
at the University of Turin and Polifonia Advisory Board member**

Programme

- 13.00-13.15 Introduction into the project and thoughts on (long-term) impact of the Polifonia project
(Peter van Kranenburg) [10' presentation 5' questions]
- 13.15-13.45 The Research Ecosystem approach of the Polifonia project
(Enrico Daga) [25' presentation 5' questions]
- 13.45-14.00 The dynamic nature of Data Management in a research project
(Andrea Scharnhorst) 10' presentation 5' questions]
- 14.00-14.30 Panel round with experts from other projects and ERIC's

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EXPERT ROUND

Dr. Femmy Admiraal
Senior data management expert at Leiden University Libraries,
former Chief Data Officer of the CLARIAH.nl project, and part of the DARIAH ERIC Coordination

Dr. Suzanne Dumochel
Head of International Cooperation, CNRS (Directorate of Open Research Data), OPERAS

Barbara Magagna – FAIR development coordinator of the GO FAIR Foundation,
member of the EOSC Task Force Semantic Interoperability

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Motivation

Polifonia focuses on European Musical Heritage, intended as musical contents and artefacts - or music objects - (tunes, scores, melodies, notations, etc.) along with relevant knowledge about them such as: their links to tangible objects (theatres, conservatoires, churches, etc.), their cultural and historical contexts, and so on.

The overall goal of the project is to realise an **ecosystem** of computational methods and tools supporting discovery, extraction, encoding, interlinking, classification, exploration of, and access to, musical heritage knowledge on the Web.

This webinar presents the specific Data Management Strategy of Polifonia (set up as management of research components of the type Data, Tools and Reports). Peter van Krannenburg presents the project briefly, Enrico Daga details the Polifonia Research Ecosystem, Andrea Scharnhorst shows how RDM can be supported by the Ecosystem.

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Panel round and discussion**Questions to the experts**

- Feedback to the presentations and in particular the Polifonia Research Ecosystem
- Share own experiences with making project output sustainable by fostering reusability
- Share ideas with us how to improve our impact strategy in Polifonia

Audience

Marloes Bontje and Andrea Scharnhorst are our Zoom-angels and will monitor the chat. If you have a question, please put it into the chat. We are looking forward to your engagement.

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Polifonia – A digital harmonizer for musical heritage knowledge (Introduction into the project and thoughts on (long-term) impact of the Polifonia project)

The Project

POLIFONIA Consortium

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8	NISV	STICHTING NEDERLANDS INSTITUUT VOOR BEELD EN GELUID	Netherlands
9	KNAW	KONINKLIJKE NEDERLANDSE AKADEMIE VAN WETENSCHAPPEN	Netherlands
10	DP	DIGITAL PATHS	Italy

www.polifonia-project.eu

The Project

The Project

Polifonia is a 3M€ project funded by the EU Horizon 2020 Programme that will run from January 2021 until April 2024 to recreate the **connections** between music, people, places and events from the sixteenth century to the modern day. These findings will be available to everyone as an interconnected global database on the web – a **knowledge graph** – and will enhance our understanding of European musical heritage.

The Polifonia consortium is an interdisciplinary team of passionate researchers and music lovers: computer scientists, anthropologists and ethnomusicologists, historians of music, linguists, musical heritage archivists, cataloguers and administrators, and creative professionals.

Polifonia in numbers

- Budget: 3,046,154 €
- 40 Months
- 8 Work Packages
- 10 pilots
- 4 Milestones
- 10 Partners
- 374 Person/Months
- 45 Tasks
- 58 deliverables
- 5 Objectives

www.polifonia-project.eu

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Polifonia | 2024

Work Packages

4

Polifonia | 2020

10 Pilot Projects

Pilot Overview

The diagram illustrates the Polifonia pilot projects, organized into three main categories: Preserving, Studying, and Interacting. Each category contains five specific projects represented by colored circles with icons and labels.

- Preserving:**
 - ORGANS:** Represented by a purple circle with an organ icon.
 - BELLS:** Represented by a purple circle with a bell icon.
 - TONALITIES:** Represented by an orange circle with a musical staff icon.
 - TUNES:** Represented by an orange circle with a musical staff icon.
 - MEETUPS:** Represented by a green circle with a network icon.
- Studying:**
 - INTERLINK:** Represented by a red circle with a network icon.
 - FACETS:** Represented by a purple circle with a geometric icon.
 - MUSICBO:** Represented by an orange circle with a musical staff icon.
 - CHILD:** Represented by an orange circle with a musical staff icon.
 - ACCESS:** Represented by a green circle with a musical staff icon.
- Interacting:**
 - led:** Represented by a red circle with a musical staff icon.

Supporting images include: an organ, a bell, a manuscript page, a person reading a book, a social media post, a data visualization, a tree diagram, a building, and a person presenting.

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	<p>The ORGANS Knowledge Graph Team: Peter van Kranenburg Link to the website More →</p>
	<p>TUNES KG The TUNES Knowledge Graph Team: Peter van Kranenburg Link to the website More →</p>
	<p>MOZ Muziekopnamen Zendgemachtigden (Dutch Broadcast Concert Collection) Team: Mari Wigham, Willem Melder, Govert Brinkmann Link to the website Dataset Blog SPARQL Endpoint More →</p>
	<p>MusicBO Knowledge Graph The Knowledge Graph about the role of Bologna in the European musical landscape. Team: Arianna Graciotti, Valentina Carriero, Rocco Tripodi, Eleonora Marzi, Fiorella Cirroku GitHub Link to SPARQL endpoint More →</p>
	<p>JAMS Ontology The JAMS Ontology Team: Jacopo de Berardinis, Andrea Poltronieri, Valentina Presutti, Albert Merono-Penuela GitHub</p>

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[ECOSYSTEM]

<https://polifonia-project.github.io/ecosystem/>

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POLIFONIA ONTOLOGY NETWORK

<https://github.com/polifonia-project/ontology-network>

Polifonia | 2024

CO-DESIGN

Polifonia | 2024

CO-DESIGN

Dispositie volgens contract 1853*	Dispositie in 2002
Grootmanuaal	Hoofdwerk
Prestant 16'	Prestant 16'
Prestant 8'	Bourdon 16'
Bourdon 8'	Prestant 8'
Octaaf 4'	Holpijp 8'
Fluit dulce 4'	Fluit harmoniek 8'
Kwint 3'	Salicionaal 8'
Octaaf 2'	Octaaf 4'
Mixtuur 4-5 st.	Kwint 3'
Fagot 16'	Octaaf 2'
Trompet 8'	Mixtuur 4-5 st.
Bovenmanuaal	Cornet 5 st.
Prestant 8'	Trompet 8'
Roerfluit 8'	Zwelwerk
Viool de gambe 8'	Prestant 8'
Quintadeen 8'	Bourdon 8'
Prestant 4'	Quintadeen 8'
Roerfluit 4'	Viola 8'
Super octaaf 2'	Vox Celestes 8'
Woudfluit 2'	Fluit harmoniek 4'
Dulciaan 8'	Violon 4'
Pedaal	Flageolet 2'
Subbas 16'	Sesquialter 2-3 st.
Prestant 8'	Mixtuur 4 st.
Octaaf 4'	Trompet 8'
Basson 16'	Fagot Hautbois 8'
<input type="checkbox"/> Copy table	Pedaal
	Kontrabass 16'
	Subbas 16'
	Open bas 8'
	Gedekt 8'

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Polifonia
Thanks

www.polifonia-project.eu
github.com/polifonia-project

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The slide features a central graphic of a starburst with multiple lines radiating from a central point, colored in shades of cyan and green. The background is black.

The Polifonia Ecosystem

 Polifonia

The Polifonia Ecosystem

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The slide features a graphic of three interconnected circular nodes. One node is purple, and two are red. They are connected by red lines. The background is black.

Motivation

What to do with project outputs?

- The breadth of a collaborative research project like Polifonia
- Research Data Management (and Plan)
- Governance: identifying and cataloguing (heterogeneous) outputs

- Acquiring metadata
- Assess compliance with FAIR principles.

- Impact of project outputs: foster reuse
- Support licence-aware reuse

- Methodology: build on good practices
 - in (open-source) data/software development and
 - research open data publishing

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The Polifonia Ecosystem

Objectives & Vision

The metaphor of an Ecosystem

Ecosystem

“An ecosystem (or ecological system) consists of all the organisms and the abiotic pools (or physical environment) with which they interact. The biotic and abiotic **components** are **linked together** through nutrient cycles and energy flows.”

<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ecosystem>

Research ecosystem

Components of various types (Data, Methods, Tools,)

Which are build, interconnected, and reassembled to answer different research questions (defined as requirements for specific problem solutions (*Polifonia* -> *Pilots*))

Polifonia implements a digital ecosystem for European Musical Heritage: music research objects (data, software, documentation).

- “Lightweight” collection of data/tools/guides for stakeholders to pick & mix (rather than a monolithic “heavy” integrated system)
- Achieve coherence as coordination – to avoid redundancy and foster integration
- To ensure FAIR research: document the musical research objects' life-cycle

The Polifonia Ecosystem

Position of the Ecosystem in the overall knowledge management

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Polifonia Ecosystem

Approach

zenodo

We produce and curate ecosystem annotations on the Polifonia GitHub organisation, following open-source development best practices.

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Polifonia Ecosystem
Data

Data are digital object that specifies, describes, or represents facts about the project's domain of interest. These include various types of digital objects such as datasets, corpora, ontologies, or repositories.

Software and applications (Tools)

Software is any digital object that is being produced by the project to achieve a certain task computationally.

Applications are executable systems and tools produced by the project for the end-user to achieve a certain task computationally.

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Polifonia Ecosystem
Reports

Reports are any digital object that specifies, describes, or represents facts about the project's domain of interest. Reports differ from data as they are mainly directed to human consumption, rather than computational treatment.

Licences

The ecosystem framework uses the Licences KG (WP2) to categorise components.

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Polifonia Ecosystem

Annotation Schema

Container types:

- Project
- WorkingGroup
- WorkPackage
- Task
- UseCase
- Pilot

Component types:

- Data
 - Dataset
 - Schema
 - Repository
 - Registry
 - Ontology
 - Corpus
 - Lexicon
 - KnowledgeGraph

- Software
 - Workflow
 - API
 - UserInterface
 - SoftwareLibrary
 - DockerImageContainer
 - Notebook
 - Script
- Application
 - WebSite
 - WebApplication
 - WebService
 - SPARQLEndpoint
 - MobileApp
 - CLITool

- Report
 - RequirementsCollection
 - Story
 - Persona
 - Mockup
 - Survey
 - InPresenceSurvey
 - FocusGroup
 - Documentation
 - Tutorial
 - EvaluationReport

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Polifonia Ecosystem

Annotation Schema

- component-id
- type
- name
- description
- image
- logo
- work-package
- pilot
- project
- resource
- demo

- release-date
- release-number
- release-link
- doi
- changelog
- licence
- copyright
- contributors

- related-components
 - informed-by
 - use-case
 - story
 - persona
 - documentation
 - evaluated-in
 - extends
 - reuses
 - serves
 - generated-by
 - derived-from

- bibliography
 - published-in
 - main-publication
 - publication
 - main-report
 - report
 - deliverable-document
- credits

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Polifonia Ecosystem

Relations among components

Polifonia Ecosystem

Licences (in progress)

- [CQ1] Do you want to reuse an external dataset?
- [CQ2] Does the license covering the dataset permit to share?
- [CQ3] If yes, what are the license requirements for sharing the data?
- [CQ4] Do you want to modify the existing dataset?
- [CQ5] Does the license covering the dataset permit to modify the original data?
- [CQ6] If yes, what are the license requirements for modifying the data?
- [CQ7] Does the license impose a ShareAlike obligation?
- [CQ8] Does the license impose any commercial restrictions?

<https://www.w3.org/ns/odrl/2/>

<https://www.dalicc.net/>

Licences

Licence	Use code
GNU Affero General Public License	AGPL
Academic Free License 3.0	AcademicFreeLicense30
Adaptive Public License 1.0	AdaptivePublicLicense10
Apache License, Version 1.1	Apache-1.1
Apache License, Version 2.0	Apache-2.0
Apple Public Source License 2.0	ApplePublicSourceLicense20
Artistic License 2.0	ArtisticLicense20

```

Polifonia Ecosystem
Annotation Schema

---
component-id: fabulous-component-source-code
type: Software
name: The Fabulous Source Code
description: Source code of The Fabulous
logo: https://www.example.org/logo.png
work-package:
- WP1
- WP2
pilot:
- ThePilot
project: a-fabulous-project
resource: https://github.com/fabulous-inc/repol/releases
demo: https://www.example.org/fabulous/demo
release-date: 2023/01/18
release-number: v1.0-alpha
release-link: https://github.com/fabulous-inc/repol/releases/tag/v0.8.1
doi: 10.5281/zenodo.000000
changelog: https://github.com/fabulous-inc/repol/releases/tag/v0.8.1
licence:
- Apache-2.0
copyright: "Copyright (c) 2023 Fabulous, Inc"
contributors:
- A developer <http://www.example.org>
...

...
related-components:
- informed-by:
  - fabulous-requirements
- use-case:
  - fabulous-uc
- story:
  - fabulous-story
- persona:
  - fabulous-persona
- documentation:
  - fabulous-component-docs
  - fabulous-component-tutorials
- extends:
  - "A Java project Jena https://www.example.org"
- reuses:
  - "Apache Camel https://camel.apache.org/"
- generated-by:
  - The AI code generator http://www.my-software-factory.com
- evaluated-in:
  - fabulous-evaluation
credits: "This project has received funding from the Lorem Ipsum Funder research and innovation programme under grant agreement 01234556."
---

# The Fabulous Component

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exercitation ullamco laboris nisi ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat. Duis aute irure dolor in reprehenderit in voluptate velit esse cillum dolore eu fugiat nulla pariatur. Excepteur sint occaecat cupidatat non proident, sunt in culpa qui officia deserunt mollit anim id est laudam
    
```

SPARQL Anything

Docs » Home Edit on GitHub

SPARQL ANYTHING

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.6524088
License Apache 2.0
How to cite
Java 11 passing
Java 14 passing
Java 17 passing

SPARQL Anything

SPARQL Anything is a system for Semantic Web re-engineering that allows users to ... query anything with SPARQL.

Main features:

- Query files in plain SPARQL 1.1, via the `SERVICE <x-sparql-anything>` (see [configuration](#)) and build knowledge graphs with `CONSTRUCT` queries
- **Supported formats:** XML, JSON, CSV, HTML, Excel, Text, Binary, EXIF, File System, Zip/Tar, Markdown, YAML, Bibtex, DOCx (see [configuration](#))
- Transforms [files](#), [inline content](#), or [the output of an external command](#)
- Full fledged **HTTP client** to query Web APIs (headers, authentication, all methods supported)
- **Functions library** for RDF sequences, strings, hashes, easy entity building, ...
- Combine multiple `SERVICE` clauses into complex data integration queries (thanks to SPARQL)
- Query templates (using [BASIL variables](#))
- Save and reuse SPARQL [Results Sets](#) as input for [parametric queries](#)
- Slice large CSV files with an iterator-like execution style (soon [JSON](#) and [XML](#))
- Supports an [on-disk option](#) (with Apache Jena TDB2)

Concept

SPARQL Anything uses a single generic abstraction for all data source formats called Facade-X.

sparql-anything.cc

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Producing annotations

Guidelines from a Polifonia Ecosystem Annotation Workshop

How many components?

- Look at component types for an inspiration
- *Data, Software, Documentation*

Do you have a container?

- If there is an umbrella activity (beyond the Polifonia WPs/Pilots)?

You MUST

- Include a `.md` file for each component/container

You SHOULD

- Have more than one component (but not more than you can handle!)

You SHOULD NOT

- Have more than one container

You MAY

- Reuse the main README.md file
- Describe resources that are not managed in the repository
- Collect all `.md` files in a folder `ecosystem``

In the case of SPARQL Anything, we have:

- SPARQL Anything (Project) → Container!
- Java Source Code (Software)
- Python Library (SoftwareLibrary)
- Command line interface (CLITool)
- Fuseki Server (WebApplication)
- Online documentation (Documentation)
- Docker container (DockerImageContainer)
- A list of tutorials (Tutorial)
- Requirements (RequirementsCollection)

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Reeco Annotations Validator

Enter GitHub repository URL

GitHub repository URL

Tree (defaults to "main")

Submit

Reeco Annotations Validator

[Back](#)

Report

Repository

https://github.com/polifonia-project/patterns-knowledge-graph (main) [🔗](#) 4 files found.

List of files:

[P2KG-Pipeline/readme.md](#) [🔗](#)

[README.md](#) [🔗](#)

[patterns-knowledge-graph-datasets/README.md](#) [🔗](#)

[queries/README.md](#) [🔗](#)

Validation report

[P2KG-Pipeline/readme.md](#) [🔗](#)

🔴 Key 'demo' error: URL cannot be resolved. File: [P2KG-Pipeline/readme.md](#) [🔗](#)

[README.md](#) [🔗](#)

🟢 No errors found.

🟡 Key 'funder' error: The activity should have at least one funding organisation. File: [README.md](#) [🔗](#)

[patterns-knowledge-graph-datasets/README.md](#) [🔗](#)

🔴 Key 'demo' error: URL cannot be resolved. File: [patterns-knowledge-graph-datasets/README.md](#) [🔗](#)

[queries/README.md](#) [🔗](#)

🔵 Not a component: no annotations found File: [queries/README.md](#) [🔗](#)

The screenshot shows the GitHub organization page for 'polifonia-project'. The navigation bar includes Overview, Repositories (113), Projects (2), Packages, Teams, People (52), and Settings. The main content area features a featured repository 'Polifonia H2020' with a description: 'Playing the soundtrack of our history' and 31 followers. Below this is a search bar and a section for the 'Polifonia Ecosystem (v2.0)', which is described as 'Data, software, and documentation of the output of the EU H2020 project Polifonia'. A sidebar on the left lists various ecosystem components like Work packages, Pilots, Requirements, Data, Tools, Reports, Licences, Changelog, and RuleBook. On the right, a list of repositories is shown, including 'bells-ontology', 'patterns-knowledge-graph', 'music-analysis-ontology', 'tonalities_pilot', 'meetups-application', and 'tunes-knowledge-graph', each with its own description and update status.

<https://polifonia-project.github.io/ecosystem/>

The screenshot displays SPARQL code for defining a schema and a service. The code includes prefixes for xsd, schema, fabio, and frapo, followed by a CONSTRUCT block for defining a 'Collection' class with various properties. A WHERE clause is used to filter results. The SERVICE blocks define external SPARQL endpoints for finding .md files and extracting YAML frontmatter.

```

5 PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
6 PREFIX schema: <https://schema.org/>
7 PREFIX fabio: <http://purl.org/spar/fabio/>
8 PREFIX frapo: <http://purl.org/cerif/frapo/>
9
10 CONSTRUCT {
11   # --> Step 6. Construct Knowledge Graph (when the Ontology evolves, change this!!!)
12   # Container triples:
13   ?container a schema:Collection, ?Type ;
14     schema:identifier ?id ;
15     schema:title ?title ;
16     schema:abstract ?description ;
17     schema:image ?image ;
18     schema:logo ?logo ;
19     schema:funding ?grants ;
20     schema:creditText ?creditText ;
21     schema:isPartOf ?work ;
22     schema:citation ?measures ;
23     schema:subjectOf ?project ;
24     schema:hasPart ?parameters ;
25
90
91   WHERE {
92
93     SERVICE <x-sparql-anything:> {
94
95       SERVICE <x-sparql-anything:> {
96
97         SERVICE <x-sparql-anything:> {
98           # --> Step 1. Find all .md files in relevant repositories (when the sources evolve, change
99             fx:properties fx:location ".ecosystem/content/_polifonia-project/external-components" ;
100             fx:archive.matches ".*.md" .
101           [] fx:anySlot ?file .
102         }
103         # --> receives iterator over a query solution ( ?file )
104       }
105       BIND ( ?file as ?componentFile ) .
106
107       # --> Step 2. extract the YAML frontmatter from files with component annotations
108       fx:properties fx:location ?componentFile .
109       [] a xyz:YamlFrontMatter ; fx:anySlot ?yaml
110     }
111   }

```

schema.org

SPARQL ANYTHING

<https://github.com/SPARQL-Anything/showcase-polifonia-ecosystem>

Polifonia Ecosystem

Intermediate validation survey (internal, 11 responses)

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Polifonia Ecosystem

Next

A reusable method and toolkit for metadata management of collaborative research projects

Libraries and Tools
(e.g. validation of annotations, recommending annotations)

Automation via GitHub actions

Validation on other EU projects

(Yours?)

SPARQL ANYTHING

Validation / Feedback

Expanding FAIR solutions across EOSC

Publishing
 RO-Crate

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Thank you for your attention
Questions?

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Design of the Ecosystem

Figure 4.1: The Polifonia Ecosystem: overview of the components and main relations. Connection points in black represent connections to all the components.

The dynamic nature of Data Management in a research project

The dynamic nature of Data Management in a research project

Presentation

**Polifonia Research Ecosystem – Impact of a project
A webinar on Data re-use and workflows**

Andrea Scharnhorst

January 19, 2024

Why DMP executing is still felt as a burden?

Why than bother with DMP?

- Open Science: Opening the blackbox of research to make research better (effective, transparent)
- Data as assets: digitisation and web enabling data to leave 'silos' and become re-purposed
- Simply a funding requirement

How to solve the problem?

- EC: specific project suits for FAIR Data, Open Science, ... to support researchers in/with data stewardship and research data management
- The Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP) is one example to introduce a standard in research data documentation and management
- Polifonia:
 - Integrated DMP (planning and practice) in the overall project management – culminating in the Research Ecosystem as an executable Research Data/Tool/Report Management Plan
 - Iterative DMP's (version 1-3)
 - applied the ORDP in the DMP documentation for each iteration

Data Management Plan

Open Research Data Pilot in Horizon 2020

1. DATA SUMMARY	2. FAIR DATA	3. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES	4. DATA SECURITY	5. ETHICAL ASPECTS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is the purpose of the data collection/ generation and its relation to the objectives of the project? • What types and formats of data will the project generate/ collect? • Will you re-use any existing data and how? • What is the origin of the data? • What is the expected size of the data? • To whom might it be useful ('data utility')? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Making data findable, including provisions for metadata (versions, keywords, naming conventions) • Making data openly accessible • Making data interoperable (ontologies) • Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the costs for making data FAIR in your project? • How will these be covered? • Who will be responsible for data management in your project? • Are the resources for long term preservation discussed (costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What provisions are in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data)? • Is the data safely stored in certified repositories for long term preservation and curation? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA). • Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

From open questions to automatisisation

Research Data Management Plans (as recommended by GOFAIR)

- [Data Stewardship Wizard](#) created by ELIXIR CZ and NL
- [DMPonline](#) of the Digital Curation Centre (DCC), UK
- [DMPTool](#) of University of California Curation Center of the California Digital Library (CDL), USA
- [RDMO Research Data Management Organiser](#) of the German Research Foundation, Germany
- [Data Management Plan Catalogue](#) of the LIBER Research Data Management Working Group
- [Practical Guide on Research Data Management](#), developed by experts from Science Europe Member Organisations

<https://www.go-fair.org/resources/rdm-starter-kit/>

• DMP Version 1-2-3

ORDP - section	DMP Version 1	DMP Version 2	DMP Version 3
Data Summary	Data sources description Pilots Co-design of survey	Survey (iterated, extended and data-mined) 2.1.1. Data sources Pilots (updated Table) 2.1.2. Polifonia Data sources as part of the Polifonia Research Ecosystem 2.1.3.	Overview about the Polifonia Ecosystem components of type DATA Cross-links to the Data sources Pilot Table Example of Bell's ontology as a Data component in the Research Ecosystem
FAIR Data	FAIR aspects discussion per Pilot	Polifonia Ontology Network 2.2.1. Polifonia Knowledge Graph 2.2.2. The Polifonia 10 Rules for Open Science 2.2.3. FAIR protocol sections 2.2.4. Polifonia Software Guidelines 2.2.5. (including Software deliverable checklist)	Answers to the FAIR question in the ORDP template based on the Research Ecosystem rules Polifonia's approach to FAIR as a process: the new FAIR section in each deliverable
Allocation of Resources	Design of the Polifonia Ecosystem	Polifonia GitHub instance 2.3.1. Implementation of the Polifonia Research Ecosystem 2.3.2. (including Rulebook and Annotation scheme) Polifonia Portal 2.3.3.	Overview about the Polifonia Github instance Outlook to the Polifonia Portal
Data Security	Design of the Polifonia Ecosystem	Polifonia Zenodo community 2.4.1. (including Guidelines)	Overview about the Polifonia Github instance
Ethical Aspects	-	Licences 2.5.	Formalisation and validation of licences as part of the Annotations of Polifonia Ecosystem components
Other Aspects	Awareness raising (webinar)	Polifonia's documentation strategy 2.6.1. Intependencies of guidelines Overviews as Appendices Updated Table on Pilot sources/ FAIR protocol section (for DL's) / Overview on Licences	Polifonia's approach to encourage reusability and reproducible open science

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Timeline of Polifonia Research Ecosystem

Data

This section collects project outputs that are released as *data*. The ecosystem considers data any digital object that specifies, describes, or represents facts about the project's domain of interest. These include various types of digital objects such as *datasets*, *corpora*, *ontologies*, or *repositories*.

■ Corpus ■ Dataset ■ KnowledgeGraph ■ Lesson ■ Ontology ■ Repository
■ Schema

Tools

This section collects project outputs that are released as software or application.

■ Application ■ CLITool ■ DockerImageContainer ■ SPARQLEndpoint ■ Software
■ SoftwareLibrary ■ UserInterface ■ WebApplication

Reports

This section collects project outputs that are released as *report*. The ecosystem considers reports any digital object that specifies, describes, or represents facts about the project's domain of interest. Reports differ from *data* as they are mainly directed to human consumption, rather than computational treatment. Reports include various types of digital objects such as *documentation*, *tutorial*, *requirements collections*, *stories* or *persona specifications*.

■ Documentation ■ Persona ■ RequirementsCollection ■ Story ■ Tutorial

<https://polifonia-project.github.io/ecosystem/> Access December 4, 2023

<https://web.archive.org/web/20231204165657/https://polifonia-project.github.io/ecosystem/>

Why DMP executing is still felt as a burden?

Polifonia's answer

Between 'Documentation catastrophe' and Blackbox

Look for intermediare levels: research components mimicking the 'knowledge units' (which are always composed by even smaller units – and focuss on their function in a larger context) = **Research Ecosystem**

